

CANADA

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
ONLINE CONFERENCE

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION

23 JULY
2025 YEAR

CANADA, OTTAWA

**INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND
RESEARCH IN EDUCATION**
International scientific-online conference

Part 40
July 23rd
COLLECTIONS OF SCIENTIFIC WORKS

CANADA 2025

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION: a collection scientific works of the International scientific online conference (23rd July, 2025) – Canada, Ottawa : "CESS", 2025. Part 40–70 p.

Chief editor:

Candra zonyfar - PhD Universitas Buana Perjuangan Karawang, Indonesia
Sunmoon University, South Korea.

Editorial board:

Martha Merrill - PhD Kent State University, USA

David Pearce - ScD Washington, D.C., USA

Emma Sabzalieva - PhD Toronto, Canada

Languages of publication: русский, english, казакша, o'zbek, limba română, кыргыз тили, Հայերէն....

The collection consists of scientific research of scientists, graduate students and students who took part in the International Scientific online conference

"INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION".

Which took place in Ottawa on July 23, 2025.

Conference proceedings are recommended for scientists and teachers in higher education establishments. They can be used in education, including the process of post - graduate teaching, preparation for obtain bachelors' and masters' degrees. The review of all articles was accomplished by experts, materials are according to authors copyright. The authors are responsible for content, researches results and errors.

© "CESS", 2025
© Authors, 2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS	
Махамедова Маликахон Шавкат кизи <i>РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИЯ МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ</i>	5
Sultanova Jayrona Doniyor qizi <i>KHOREZM FOLKLORE IN THE CONTEXT OF FAIRY TALES: THEORETICAL APPROACHES AND TYPOLOGICAL STUDY</i>	11
Sheraliyev Odiljon Akbar ugli <i>TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY – A FACTOR IN ACHIEVING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.</i>	15
D.Jabborov R.Akbaraliyeva <i>IQTISODIYOTNI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH SHAROITIDA SOLIQ IMTIYOZLARINING AHAMIYATI</i>	21
Каримов Нуриддин Пайзуллаевич <i>ВЛИЯНИЕ ОРОШЕНИЯ ОЗИМОЙ ПШЕНИЦЫ НА СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ЗЕРНОВОГО БЕЛКА В УСЛОВИЯХ ОРОШАЕМЫХ СВЕТЛО-СЕРЫХ ПОЧВ</i>	26
Samiyev M.A. <i>THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL BASES OF POVERTY REDUCTION THROUGH DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN THE REGIONS AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES</i>	31
Saidzoda Shakhlokhon Murodilloyevna <i>OPPORTUNITIES AND SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF CULTURAL HERITAGE MANAGEMENT IN TOURIST AREAS</i>	35
Tolliyev E.M. <i>WAYS TO DEVELOP SERVICE ENTERPRISES THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES</i>	38
Jumayev Davronbek To'raqul o'g'li <i>ISSUES OF LEGAL REGULATION OF THE USE OF TRANSBOUNDARY RIVERS IN CENTRAL ASIA</i>	41
Norboyev Bobomurod Abduraim o'g'li <i>QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'I NING XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARGA TA'SIRI</i>	46
Sattorova Shokhsanamkhon Isokjon kizi <i>THE HISTORICAL PERIODS OF HOTEL INDUSTRY IN TOURISM</i>	54
Жалилова Озода Ўлмас кизи <i>СУДНИ, СУДЯНИ ЁКИ ОДИЛ СУДЛОВНИ АМАЛГА ОШИРИШДА ИШТИРОК ЭТУВЧИ БОШҚА ШАХСНИ ЁКИ СУД МУҲОКАМАСИ ИШТИРОКЧИСИНИ ҲАҚОРАТ ҚИЛИШ: ЖИНОЯТ ҚОНУНЧИЛИГИ ВА КРИМИНАЛИСТИК ЖИҲАТЛАР.</i>	57
Turakulova Shokhsanam Ulugbekovna <i>GREEN ECONOMY: THE ART OF HARNESSING LIFE'S. OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT</i>	63

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL BASES OF POVERTY REDUCTION THROUGH DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN THE REGIONS AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES

Samiyev M.A.

*Intern-assistant of the Department
of "Economic Theory", SamIES*

Abstract. *This article studies the theoretical foundations, practical directions and experiences of foreign countries in reducing poverty through the development of the service sector in the regions. The role of the service sector in increasing employment, expanding sources of income for the population, and activating the local economy is analyzed. Based on foreign experience, proposals and recommendations for the development of the service sector in the regions of Uzbekistan have been developed.*

Keywords: *service sector, poverty reduction, regional development, employment, source of income, entrepreneurship, foreign experience, socio-economic reforms.*

Poverty reduction is one of the most important goals in the economic policy of any country. In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has also identified the development of the service sector as one of the priority areas in the fight against poverty. After all, the service sector allows for the creation of jobs with minimal investment, is an industry open to small and medium-sized businesses, and provides opportunities for various segments of the population to operate. In the modern world, poverty is one of the global problems that has a serious impact on socio-economic development. The issue of poverty reduction is in the focus of attention of international organizations, states and civil society, and effective strategies and programs have been developed in different countries in this regard. Developed and developing countries of the world have accumulated significant experience in creating advanced mechanisms for poverty reduction.

Various studies have been conducted by domestic and foreign scientists on poverty reduction, and a number of theoretical and practical approaches have been formed in this direction. Among domestic studies, the works of Uzbek scientists, including economists such as Kh. Abdukarimov and Sh. Buriyev, can be noted. Their studies provide a thorough analysis of the effectiveness of state policy, economic reforms, and social programs in reducing poverty. In particular, the importance of developing local entrepreneurship and attracting investments in the fight against poverty is emphasized. Among foreign studies, the works of scientists such as P. Collier, J. Sachs, and A. Sen occupy an important place. P. Collier's work "The Bottom Billion" analyzes the causes of poverty deepening and ways to prevent

it. J. Sachs, in his book "The End of Poverty", puts forward economic strategies for developing countries. A. Sen, considering poverty as a factor affecting human development, emphasizes the importance of economic opportunities and access to education.

Foreign experiences are of great importance in reducing poverty, as they show the effectiveness of successful strategies and policies implemented in other countries. Foreign experiences help countries to introduce approaches that are appropriate for their own conditions. The importance of foreign experiences includes learning and implementing effective policies, introducing innovative solutions and technologies, and adapting to social and economic changes. Poverty reduction policies and programs implemented in foreign countries allow us to learn from their successes and shortcomings, learn from their best practices, and implement them in our own country. For example, programs such as Bolsa Família in Brazil or the specialized social assistance system in Germany can be a model for interaction and changing social conditions. Foreign experiences allow us to learn new technologies and innovative approaches. Innovative solutions such as mobile payment systems in Africa, South Korea's technology development model, or Singapore's startup-friendly environment have all had effective results in reducing poverty. By adapting these technologies to your own country, you can reduce poverty.

The potential of the services sector in poverty reduction

1. Creating sources of income through the development of entrepreneurship. Small services - for example, hairdressing, tailoring, repair services, local transport and logistics - can become a convenient source of income for the most vulnerable segments of the population. Microloans and subsidies provided by the state will accelerate this process.

2. Ensuring employment through a system of vocational training and advanced training. Many types of services do not require a special higher or technical education. Therefore, short-term vocational training courses can provide employment to representatives of the poor. This will strengthen their social protection.

3. Using digital services and modern technologies. New sources of income are emerging through online services (freelance, online lessons, e-commerce, design and marketing services), especially among young people and women. This process can be accelerated by increasing digital literacy in the regions.

4. Developing tourism and the service sector. New jobs are being created, especially in historical regions (Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva), through local services - guides, transportation, hotels, and national catering. This directly contributes to poverty reduction.

With the help of foreign experiences in the efficient use of resources and efficiency, it is possible to learn about the effective use of resources necessary for poverty reduction and their proper distribution. Economic efficiency can be achieved in poverty reduction through microcredits, social assistance programs, support for small businesses, and effective management of other resources. In the context of adaptation to local conditions, foreign experiences should be implemented in a manner adapted to specific local conditions. Programs and policies implemented to reduce poverty should be adapted to the specific social, economic, and cultural conditions of each country. Foreign experiences help in developing approaches that are appropriate to local conditions. In the process of ensuring social equality and justice, foreign experiences pay special attention to ensuring social equality and justice in reducing poverty. Policies implemented in other countries show the importance of ensuring social justice and creating equal opportunities for all citizens. For example, programs like Bolsa Família in Brazil have been successful in reducing poverty and ensuring equity.

In conclusion, in today's era, when the level of regional poverty is increasing due to climate change, anthropogenic impacts, rising prices, inflation, external debt and budget deficit, the increase in the number of poor and backward people cannot but negatively affect the macroeconomic indicators of the country. For this reason, at the government level, providing maximum support to every citizen, especially those who are in dire need of material assistance, remains a priority. Along with this, initiatives such as providing them with jobs or training in entrepreneurship are among them. However, if the economy is not stable, both wages and the standard of living of the population will continue to decline.

The development of the service sector is one of the effective means of combating poverty. This sector provides not only sources of income, but also employment and social stability. By further deepening reforms in this area in Uzbekistan, it is possible to reduce regional inequalities and consistently reduce poverty levels.

REFERENCES:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Mahallada tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish, aholi bandligini ta'minlash va kambag'allikni qisqartirish bo'yicha davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlari to'g'risida" PF-29-son farmoni. 03.12.2021 yil. <https://lex.uz>.
2. Махмудов О.Х. Оилаларда камбағалликни қисқартириш омиллари. "Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar" ilmiy elektron jurnali. № 6, noyabrdekabr, 2021 yil, 267-276 бетлар.

3. Калонов М. “Камбағалликни қисқартириш: имконият ва ҳаракатлар қандай натижа беради?” «Халқ сўзи» газетасининг 2021 йил 11 февраль 30- сони.
4. Ravallion, M. (2016). The Economics of Poverty: History, Measurement, and Policy. Oxford University Press.
5. ILO (International Labour Organization). (2019). Decent Work and Economic Growth: A Pathway to Poverty Reduction. Geneva: ILO Publications.